

Ameliorating Effect of the Ethanol Root Extract of *Anthocleista djalonenis* on Sexual Parameters in Paroxetine-Induced Male Infertility in Wistar Rats

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Abstract

Anthocleista djalonenis (Cabbage tree), a plant native to West Africa, is used in various ethnomedicinal practices. It is used locally in the treatment of male sexual related infertility. This study was therefore designed to evaluate the potentials of ethanol extract of the root of *Anthocleista djalonenis* in improving sexual parameters of sexual related paroxetine-induced infertility in male wistar rats. Twenty-five male rats with average weight of 150 g were assigned to five groups, each with five rats. Group A (control) was given distilled water, while groups B to E were administered 2 mg/kg/bw paroxetine for seven days. Thereafter groups B and C were treated with 100 and 200 mg/kg/bw of the extract orally respectively, group D was administered standard drug tadalafil (10 mg/kg/bw) orally and group E remained untreated. The treatment regime lasted for 21 days after which the animals were then sacrificed. Samples were collected to evaluate the sperm indices which include viability, motility, morphology and histology of the testis, epididymis and vas deference. The results revealed a significant ($p < 0.05$) enhancement in sperm count, motility and morphology in the rats administered the extracts and these parameters were hitherto degraded by paroxetine. The effectiveness of groups administered 200 mg/kg/bw extract was comparable to Tadalafil. The histological analysis revealed that the extracts were able to significantly restore the damages inflicted by paroxetine on the epididymis and testis. The results of this study justified the use of *A. djalonenis* to combat male fertility as use by tradomedical practitioners.

Keywords: *Anthocleista djalonenis*, aroxetine, epidydemis, sperm count, vas deference,

1.0 Introduction

Over time, medicinal herbs have been utilized for treating a variety of illnesses and conditions^[1]. Around 80% of the global population continues to depend on traditional remedies and local medicines primarily sourced from plant extracts^[3]. It is important to highlight the increasing popularity of herbal medicine in developing nations. Currently, traditional Nigerian medicines are used to address a variety of health issues such as mental disorders, sleep problems, fractures, infertility, and other reproductive health issues^[3]. Incorporating aphrodisiacs into a healthy lifestyle may lead to improved sexual satisfaction^[4].

Sexual problems may arise during any phase of the sexual response process. It prevents individuals from experiencing pleasure during sexual activities, including physical pleasure, desire, decision-making, arousal, and orgasm^[5]. The World Health Organization defined sexual dysfunction as the inability to effectively participate in a sexual relationship^[6]. Several reasons can contribute to this sickness, such as physical factors (like liver or kidney problems, diabetes, heart or vascular issues, neurological conditions, hormonal imbalances, side effects of specific medications such as antidepressants); mental factors such as stress from work, anxiety, concern about sexual abilities, depression, and guilt related to body image^[7].

Erectile dysfunction makes up most cases of male sexual dysfunction^[8]. Despite adequate sexual stimulation, delayed ejaculation is not as prevalent in different ways compared to premature ejaculation, which occurs early. The coordination of the nervous, cardiovascular, endocrine, and reproductive systems is essential for sexual activity to function properly^[9]. Data indicates that more than 150 million men worldwide are affected by erectile dysfunction (ED), with male ED cases expected to increase to 322 million by 2025^[10]. Sexual dysfunction caused by medication side effects plays a key role^[11].

There is a growing trend towards using medicinal plants instead of synthetic drugs due to a shift in focus towards traditional medicine^[12]. Around 80% of the world's population uses herbs as the basis for most traditional medications^[13]. Medicinal plants are utilized to enhance reproductive functions. Typically, while various herbal treatments are utilized for addressing various reproductive problems, natural aphrodisiacs are ingested to enhance sexual function, including issues like erectile dysfunction, low sperm count, absence of sperm, hormonal imbalances, and more^[14].

Paroxetine, a typical selective serotonin reuptake inhibitor compound has been extensively used in clinical settings. Sexual dysfunction has been reported with this compound, similar to other substances in its category^[15]. It has the capability to inhibit the formation of nitric oxide (NO), an essential regulator of smooth muscle relaxation and penile erection, in laboratory experiments and in living organisms^[16]. When administered to rats either consistently or abruptly, paroxetine diminishes their capacity to achieve erection following stimulation by the cavernosal nerve^[9]. Tadalafil, a potent and selective inhibitor of phosphodiesterase type 5 (PDE5), enhances the relaxation of the erectile tissue in humans stimulated by NO and promotes penile erection in rats following NO administration^[17].

Despite ethno-botanical research showing that the root decoction of *A. djalonensis* is used to improve sexual activity, there have been limited experimental studies conducted to validate these effectiveness claims. Modern medicine for erectile dysfunction can also be costly, difficult to access, and come with adverse effects. *A. djalonensis* is more affordable, easily found, and

widely used by people in the southern part of Nigeria in comparison to modern medicine. This research thus examined and contrasted the aphrodisiac effectiveness of ethanol extract from *A. djalonensis* root with tadalafil in mature male Wistar rats.

2.0: Materials and Methods

2.1: Collection and Authentication of Plant Material

Anthocleista djalonensis stems were purchased from herbal vendors in the New Benin Market area of Edo State Nigeria. The identification was done in the Plant Biology and Biotechnology Department, Faculty of Life Sciences, University of Benin, Benin City, and a voucher specimen (UBH-A594) was deposited.

2.2: Preparation of Plant Extract

The stalks of *Anthocleista djalonensis* were washed with water, then laid out on lab tables to dry for two weeks at room temperature before being crushed at the Pharmacy Department of the University of Benin. The plant material was then dried in an horizontal vacuum drying oven at 40 °C for 5–10 min before being ground into a fine powder using a mechanical grinder. After pulverizing, 575 grams of stem plant powder was measured and mixed with 3.7 liters of ethanol for 72 hours, then filtered through Mushlin cloth and whatman1 filter paper before concentrating the filtrate with a rotary evaporator (IKA, Germany) at 75°C. The sample was dried in a freeze drier. The ethanolic extract's percentage yield was calculated with the formula (% Yield = weight of extract/weight of powdered sample × 100/1)^[18].

2.3 Drugs and Reagents

Paroxetine, an antidepressant, and the standard medication tadalafil were purchased from a standard registered pharmacy store opposite the University of Benin Teaching Hospital in Benin city, Edo State. The standard drug was crushed into 80 mg and mixed with 200 milliliters of distilled water. All other reagents used were of analytical grade.

2.4 Experimental design

This study involved the use of twenty-five (25) male Wistar rats weighing about 150 g on the average. The animals were obtained from the animal facility of the Department of Biochemistry at the University of Benin in Benin City, Edo State, Nigeria. The groups were labeled A, B, C, D, and E. The animals were given unrestricted access to water and fed regular commercial pellets. The enclosures were sanitized on a daily basis during the duration of the research. The animals were observed each day to assess their overall health and weighed once a week. There were no negative occurrences observed prior to or during the experiment. The 25 male rats were randomly divided into five groups and received the proper treatment through oral administration. Paroxetine in the amount of 200 mg was crushed into a powder and then mixed with 1 liter of distilled water. Groups B, C, D, and E received 1.5 ml of this over the course of seven days. After that, the treatment plan started and continued for a further 21 days. Group A received a regular diet, while group B and C were administered 100 and 200 mg/kg body weight of *Anthocleista djalensis* root extract, respectively. Group D received Tadalafil standard drug at a dosage of 10ml/kg (equivalent to 5 mg/kg). The drug was administered orally through an orogastric tube.

2.5 Assay protocols

The mice's vas deferens, testis, and epididymis were removed and precisely weighed with an electronic balance from OHAUS in Hangzhou, China. The left testis of the mice was preserved using formaldehyde fixative, processed, cut into slices, and stained with hematoxylin and eosin (H&E), and the pictures were taken. The mice's left and right epididymis and vas deferens were sliced and placed in a tube with normal saline, followed by shaking and incubation in a water bath at 37 °C for 15 minutes. Sperm quality was assessed. A diluent drop was placed on the blood cell count, and the sperm count in five squares was observed using a biological microscope. The number of sperm per milliliter was equal to $N \times \text{dilution factor} \times 5 \times 10^4$. Another droplet of dispersant was used for spreading; 200 sperm cells were seen, and the count of mobile sperm cells was recorded. Furthermore, the sperm underwent staining as per the quick sperm stain kit guidelines and was observed and captured

using a fluorescence-inverted microscope–spectrometer coupling (DMI4000B+Iso Plane 160, Leica Corporation, Wetzlar, Germany)^[19].

$$\text{Sperm motility} = \frac{\text{Active sperm count}}{200} \times 100\%$$

2.6: Statistical Analysis

Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) 27, Excel 2021, GraphPad 9.3 software were utilized for both statistical analysis and creating visual representations of the data. Data were assessed through one-way ANOVA. A p-value of less than 0.05 meant significant difference, while less than 0.01 indicated very significant difference, and less than 0.001 meant extremely significant difference; all three were deemed statistically significant. Experimental findings were presented as mean \pm standard deviation ($X \pm SD$) for all instances. Multiple comparisons for the groups were done using Post Hoc Turkey (HSD) to test for the level of significance between means. A $p < 0.05$ was considered to be statistically significant.

3.0: Results and Discussion

3.1: Effects of *Anthocleista djalensis* on Sperm Count and Viability

As shown in Table 1, compared with the control (CN) group, the sperm count and sperm motility of the paroxetine (PRX) group were significantly increased ($p > 0.001$), while (*Anthocleista djalensis*) AD administration significantly improved the sperm count and sperm motility ($p < 0.001$, $p < 0.01$, and $p < 0.05$). The number of sperm, the proportion of progressive motility, viability, and morphology all showed improvements 21 days into the treatment. Sperm count showed a significant increase ($P < 0.05$) when exposed to doses of 100 and 200 mg/kg/bw of the substance extract as demonstrated in comparison to the normal and negative control. In addition, as shown on the slide PRX administration also led to abnormal sperm in male mice, such as coiled tails, curved tails, annular tails, headless, and double heads. This was consistent with the results of Tanrikut et al.^[20]. It can be seen that PRX not only causes ED in male mice, but also has an adverse effect on sperm quality in mice. These agree with the findings of Nantia et al.^[21]. The findings of this study indicate that the

extract may enhance the reproductive capabilities of male rats by boosting both the quality and quantity of sperm. This outcome may support the belief in the potential of the plant to improve the

fertilizing capability of sperm cells and its application as a fertility booster in traditional medicine.

Table 1.0: Effect of *Anthocleista djalonenensis* on the sperm motility in paroxetine-induced male infertility in wistar rats

Groups	Progressive Motility	Non-Progressive Motility	Total Motility
A (Control)	35.00±0.00 ^a	16.00±3.79 ^b	56.67±1.67 ^a
B Paroxetine +(100 mg/kg)	18.33±1.67 ^a	8.33±1.67 ^b	26.67±1.67 ^b
C Paroxetine + (200 mg/kg)	23.33±4.41 ^a	11.67±6.67 ^b	33.33±4.41 ^a
D Paroxetine + (Tadalafil)	26.67±1.67 ^a	13.33±1.67 ^b	40.00±2.88 ^a
E (Untreated)	6.67±1.67 ^a	20.00±2.89 ^a	23.33±3.33 ^a

Data are presented as Mean ±SEM, n=5

Table 2.0: Effect of *Anthocleista djalonenensis* on the sperm count and normality in paroxetine-induced male infertility in wistar rats

Groups	Sperm Count (x 10 ⁻⁶ Cells/MM ³)	Sperm Normality (%)
A Control	373.33 ± 39.29 ^a	53.33 ± 3.33 ^a
B Paroxetine + 100 mg/kg extract	216.67 ± 40.55 ^a	48.33 ± 3.33 ^a
C Paroxetine + 200 mg/kg extract	263.33 ± 18.56 ^a	35.00 ± 2.88 ^b
D Paroxetine + Tadalafil	353.33 ± 20.28 ^a	48.33 ± 10.14 ^a
E. Paroxetine (untreated)	123.33 ± 14.53 ^a	20.00 ± 2.89 ^a

The data are expressed as mean ± SD, n = 5

Effect of *Anthocleista djalonenensis* on the sperm morphology in paroxetine-induced male infertility in wistar rats.

Group A and B showed normal spermatozoon: Head, mid-piece and tail intact. Group C headless spermatozoa with bent/coiled tails.

showed, detached head and bent tail (>50% of spermatozoa), Group D, showed Abnormal morphology: Mesh work of entangled spermatozoa with bent and coiled tail; while group E showed Abnormal spermatozoa:

Plate 1.0: Effect of *Anthocleista djalonenensis* on the sperm morphology in paroxetine-induced male infertility in wistar rats.

Histopathological Analysis of the testis

According to the results of the H&E staining of Epididymis tissue in plate 2 the sectioned epididymis of the CN group shows a normal muscular layer and mucosa containing spermatozoa. Which are closely arranged. The sectioned epididymis of PRX +100mg/kg ethanol extract of AD group shows a normal muscular layer and mucosa containing spermatozoa. Which are closely arranged when compared with the CN group. The Section epididymis of PRX +200mg/kg ethanol extract of AD shows a shrunken epididymis, having a

normal muscular layer and a desquamated mucosa layer with lumen contains no spermatozoa. This shows a damaged epididymis when compared with the CN group. The Section of the epididymis of PRX + TDF shows a normal muscular layer and the mucosa containing spermatozoa. The Sectioned epididymis of PRX +NO TREATMENT shows a shrunken epididymis having a normal muscular layer and a desquamated mucosa with a lumen that contains no spermatozoa. The results of HE staining of epididymis show that AD can ameliorate the injury caused by PRX in the epididymis. The finding agrees with Okeke et al.^[22].

Plate 2.0: Effect of *Anthocleista djalonensis* on the histology of testis in paroxetine-induced male infertility in wistar rats. Pathological section analysis testis tissues: (A) represents the CN group, (B) represents the PRX +100mg/kg ethanol extract of AD group, (C) represents the PRX +200mg/kg ethanol extract of AD group (D) represents the PRX + TDF group, (E) represents the PRX group.

Histopathological Analysis of the Epididymis

Based on the H&E staining results of Epididymis tissue in Figure 3, the CN group's sectioned epididymis displays a typical muscular layer and mucosa with closely spaced spermatozoa. In comparison, the PRX +100mg/kg ethanol extract of AD group's sectioned epididymis also shows a normal muscular layer and mucosa with closely arranged spermatozoa. Meanwhile, the sectioned epididymis of PRX +200mg/kg ethanol extract of AD group exhibits a shriveled epididymis,

with a normal muscular layer and a peeled-off mucosa layer that lacks spermatozoa in the lumen. In comparison to the CN group, the epididymis appears damaged. The epididymal section of PRX + TDF exhibits a healthy muscle layer and mucosa filled with sperm. In untreated PRX +NO TREATMENT, the epididymis is smaller with a healthy muscle layer and a shedding mucosa, and its lumen is devoid of sperm cells. The HE staining results of the epididymis indicate that AD can improve the damage inflicted by PRX in the epididymis.

Plate 3.0: Effect of *Anthocleista djalensis* on the histology of epididymis in paroxetine-induced male infertility in wistar rats. Pathological section analysis of the Epididymis: (A) represents the CN group, (B) represents the PRX +100mg/kg ethanol extract of AD group, (C) represents the PRX +200mg/kg ethanol extract of AD group (D) represents the PRX + TDF group, (E) represents the PRX group.

Plate 4.0: Effect of *Anthocleista djalensis* on the histology of Vas Deferens in paroxetine-induced male infertility in wistar rats. Pathological section analysis of the Vas Deferens: (A) represents the CN group, (B) represents the PRX +100mg/kg ethanol extract of AD group, (C) represents the PRX +200mg/kg ethanol extract of AD group (D) represents the PRX + TDF group, (E) represents the PRX group.

Conclusion

The findings of the research indicate that the ethanol root extract of *A. djalensis* could have fertility-boosting benefits by enhancing sperm quantity and quality, as well as improving the structure of the testis, vas deferens, and epididymis. This research supports the idea of using the plant's roots in ethnomedicine to improve male fertility.

Recommendation

Additional research will be aimed at engaging in more extensive studies to confirm these findings, possibly with larger sample sizes and longer durations, conduct a comprehensive toxicology

studies to identify any potential side effects or contraindications and also explore the potential for developing standardized herbal supplements or pharmaceuticals based on *A. djalensis* extract. Encourage collaboration between ethnobotanists, pharmacologists, and reproductive health specialists to further explore the potential of this plant.

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